

ANDRZEJ LASON

Corrigendum to: New species of *Epuraea* (*Micruria*) from Oman (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae, Epuraeinae). *Annals of the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom, Entomology* 30(online 009): 1–7. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5801139

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ul. Wiejska 4B/85, 15-352 Białystok, Poland, e-mail: haptos@interia.pl

Abstract: Corrigendum to: New species of *Epuraea* (*Micruria*) from Oman (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae, Epuraeinae). *Annals of the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom, Entomology* 30(online 009): 1–7. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5801139.

Key words: *Epuraea* (*Micruria*) *omanica* sp. nov., erroneous number of paratypes.

In the indicated publication, in the species description section Taxonomy, on page 2, the number of paratypes was incorrectly given:

is: “**Paratypes:** 3 f*f*, OMAN same data as holotype [laser printed] // (ALBC, NMPC, USMB)”,

should: “**Paratypes:** 3 m*m*, 5 f*f*, OMAN same data as holotype [laser printed] // (ALBC, NMPC, USMB)”.

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